

Modelling and Simulation of Electrodermal Activity by Automated Concept

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Abstract

The pilot study of the project was conducted as a model study on the possibility of automating the use of Electrodermal Activity (EDA) sensors embedded in a touchpad or touchscreen device to measure skin conductance in real-time. The EDA sensor pad is based on a custom approach to studying EDA by using the skin adaptive touchpad of an Android to track and record the EDA of the skin while the users are involved in a complex study. The concept behind the mechanism of the EDA model is described and an analytical tool is used to synchronise the response reading and detect both phasic and tonic changes in the skin. Error in EDA prediction on the parametric attributes was computed for lens and inner EDA response and the result shows that there is a higher margin in error detected for inner EDA than that of the Lens (touch screen), this could be due to an error in light illumination of settings with the simulated output. Subsequent modifications will be addressed in a later study.

Keywords: Electrodermal activity, Sensor pad, Touchpad, Electrostatic, Predictive modelling, Skin adaptive.

1 Introduction

There has been some research ([15, 24, 10, 3]) on EDA studies, most of which are focusing on using a custom model to measure EDA response, one of the pilot studies conducted is studying skin conductivity in real-time in the field of education, and it is interesting to use this form of technology to access students' cognitive engagement in a classroom setting. The research on this particular area [15, 24, 10, 3, 21, 22, 16], used student participants and college teachers

by asking them to wear an Empatica E4 wristband during class periods where different activities were organised including lectures, workshops and exams. They monitored several individuals simultaneously which makes it possible to compare the collected data among students and between different students and teachers. The data generated from these wearable sensors showed different readings that represent the electrodermal activity of the participants and those of the teachers are different from those of the students.

The research made suggestions on how to improve the understanding of all the phenomena that could affect electrodermal activity measurements before applying it to draw conclusions related to cognitive engagement [17, 4, 8, 25, 20]. The EDA is arguably the most popular and most informative psychophysiological measure that has been used to study the cognitive and emotional responses of users. Other research usually begins with a review of recent evidence that has shed more light on the neural EDA. The researchers demonstrate some investigations that record EDA using a touchpad device and try to study the emotion and other higher-order cognitive processes in different areas in a neuropsychological study [11, 1, 19, 12, 7].

They integrated psychophysiology and cognitive neuroscience allowing important insights into cognitive response and memory. They used this to study the brains of adults and concluded that the inferior parietal region on the right is important for EDA connected to stimulus properties such as emotional significance and cognition [9, 23, 28, 18, 5, 27, 26]. One of the major drawbacks of using EDA is response parameters and its accuracy in response detection, this is normally due to the type of conductivity applied as an electrostatic field, which usually comes with noise and produces noisy data in response visualisation and simulation [29, 30, 2, 31, 6, 14, 13]. This paper addresses this issue by using the mechanism adapted to the touch screen and touch lens of Mobile phones as the electric conductor of signal from the skin to the lens surface. There are two kinds of structure for the module with resistive touch panels, this is (1) lens glass and (2) polycarbonate. This part of the scheme and a more common structure are also used for conductivity touch panels as a form of film/glass. The only significant difference between these two is the material at the bottom of the sensor and the accompanying support. The conductive touch sensors are made of glass as mentioned above, which are covered with electrically conductive and resistance layers (made of film coating) and covered with Indium-tin-oxide as a lens containing the light condenser, elastomer for finger contact with the lens and camera (Figure 1) that captures the image input from the lens. This also registers the moisture content of the skin surface and can be tracked continuously in short time intervals, the light conductive plate captures the image and it is reflected in the marker displaced has the HOG features using image processing.

2 Method

The measure of EDA of the skin surface is usually through the amount of electrical change so the skin as a result of sweat usually when a person is involved in a complex problem that involves a huge amount of mental workload and cognition, this can also be as a result of sweat in the skin and response state is what we measure in the

Figure 1: The EDA model framework that shows the light condenser plate and source markers for finger contact and response reading.

skin based on an unconscious thought. The amount of sweat is the moisture content contained in the skin and can be modelled and simulated in real-time in a confined environment. It is also best suitable in a non-invasive situation. Thirty participants were recruited and were asked to place their hands on the touch lens that captured the mental response and workload while they were involved in a solution to a complex mathematical problem. Given the custom method, the signal is bound to be noisy due to distraction and system integration at the pilot stage. The Savitsky Golay filter (Equation 5) was used to handle that aspect of pattern percolation. The main aim is to be able to detect and recognise natural patterns in the response reading by measuring the moisture content of the skin with the following model:

$$MC_{skin} = \frac{w_{skin_{con}} - w_{Environment}}{w_{Environment}} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

where $WC_{skin_{con}}$ = moisture content expressed as a percentage due to reaction from the skin. $w_{skin_{con}}$ = weight in skin condition to task performance. $w_{Environment}$ = weight of skin to environmental constraint.

The predicted fingerprint, in this case, is equivalent to the moisture content of the skin due to task performance and as a result of the electrical changes of the skin due to reaction to perceived stimuli this is given as:

$$X_i = MC_{skin}(t)n. \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Therefore: } \frac{d^3x}{dy^3} &= a \frac{d^2x}{dy^2} + b \frac{dx}{dy} + c; \\ x &= \int_{i=1}^n 3 \frac{d^2x}{dy^2} - 2a \frac{dx}{dy} - b; \\ y &= ax + c \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where a, b, c are constants due to environmental constraints, x represents the rate of change of conduction with the lens through the moisture content MC_{skin} as an input matrix of the sensor output produced by the

image detector, and this produces the resultant reaction y as a vector matrix, a cognitive response or reaction to stimuli on the skin surface. The skin temperature (ST) with time t is measured as:

$$\frac{d^3(ST)}{dt^3} = a \frac{d^2(ST)}{dt^2} + b \frac{d(ST)}{dt} + c; \quad (4)$$

For a custom EDA and ST response of this form, the noise is very intense, a Savitsky Golay filter (Equation 5) is used to remove noise and anomalies for a smooth representation of the response variable y . The behaviour of the filter is influenced by selecting appropriate filter coefficients. The moving average filter is a polynomial fit that smoothens the derivative by adjusting the coefficients of the equation. The data points np define the data used for the smoothing.

$$y_i = \frac{1}{2} \left[\sum_{i=\frac{np-1}{2}}^{\frac{np-1}{2}} a_i x_{t+i} \right] \quad (5)$$

3 Result

Figure 2 shows EDA readings and ST in its noisy state at initial readings, it is difficult to detect a natural response at both phasic and tonic levels. Application of signal filter will show clear peaks and readings like in Figure 3. The baseline could also be set to differentiate the readings and classify each state in the signals as belonging to a phasic or a tonic change, since both optimal tonics may be similar to a simple phasic change. The modules in each control are set to be able to differentiate a tonic phase from a phasic change by detecting optimal responses in each case.

At the time of problem-solving when the engagement of the users is a form of physical activity that has to be measured the physiological response is used as a metric for the level of cognitive load placed on the users. The induced stimuli usually make the individual respond to stimuli by reacting; i.e. sweating in large quantities or simply moist palms in sensitive people. This is usually very easy to detect when in situations such as measuring the level of cognitive engagement of a person during learning processes. Other physiological attributes can still be appended to understand the correlates and synchronisation to events during normal activity. This can help authenticate the response and design modifications. Also knowing the level of cognitive engagement of students in different circumstances would allow the optimisation processes in both modelling and simulation concepts. The measurement error can also be used for system optimisation, and this is required for the inner EDA and lens contact signal detected. Figure 4 shows the error in measurement of the EDA at response reading for a particular participant, the results show a minimal margin for both stress and relaxed cognitive state of the user

and above the estimated rate of 0.01% for the response detection.

Error detected for inner EDA at lens point has similar characteristics and little marginal fluctuations. Figure 5 shows the error record in EDA response behaviour in cognition to the complex task at lens pint. Using the response, the changes in spikes reading based on stress and the relaxed mood were recorded, from the baseline, a two-way ANOVA measure was evaluated, with data generated and found that a significant effect of EDA response at lens point change with $F(4.13) = 7.04, p \leq .001, = .8$. This is a pair-wise comparison with Bonferoni's adjustment that shows a normalised response reading at every timestamp based on aggregate response. The timestamp at the initial recording has a significantly higher EDA change than all the time intervals. A significant main effect of the condition is EDA change was found in the visual interface that holds the complex mathematical problem and recording during task engagement.

4 Conclusion

This paper attempts to investigate the automating of the cognitive concept in electrodermal activity through modelling and simulation. The pilot study started with a few participants who were recruited (thirty students, twenty male and ten female) and asked to place their first two fingers on the touchpad to record SCR while they were involved in a complex problem-solving. The EDA sensor pad is based on a custom approach to studying EDA by using the skin adaptive touchpad of an Android to track and record the EDA of the skin while the users are involved in a complex study. The concept behind the mechanism of the EDA model is described and an analytical tool is used to synchronise the response reading and detect both phasic and tonic changes in the skin. Error in EDA prediction on the parametric attributes was computed for lens and inner EDA response and the result shows that there is a higher margin in error detected for inner EDA than that of the Lens (touch screen), this could be due to an error in light illumination of settings with the simulated output. Subsequent modifications will be addressed in a later study where the analytical tool will be used to modify and integrate other physiological response metrics for advanced response measures in a multimodal scheme.

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Figure 2: Window interface from the analytical tool with a noisy EDA response reading and Skin Temperature.

Figure 3: Filtered physiological response readings with both detected optimal tonic and phasic changes that correlate to a particular event.

Figure 4: Error in EDA predictions for timestamps in both relaxed and stressed cognitive states of the participants.

Figure 5: Error in performance for EDA detection at lens point concerning time..

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